

FORMING THE SKILLS OF ARTISTIC PERCEPTION OF FINE ART WORKS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. Knowledge, skills and abilities are not the ultimate goal of education, but they are a means of developing the individuality of the student, a creative person will show a creative approach in all activities in the future.

Key words: school, knowledge, experience, student

The results of research conducted on the formation of artistic perception skills of works of art among students of general education schools show that the development of individuality in students is of special importance in the development of artistic creativity in visual arts education. the need to give, because it is a component of general artistic ability;

that the psychophysiological basis of special and creative ability is different;

artistic creative ability is expressed differently at different age stages;

to identify different aspects of the student's individuality through the diagnostic methods used in the research;

from the methods of diagnosis, to determine the general level of development, the aspects necessary for visual art activity, but not sufficiently developed in the student, and on this basis, to develop an appropriate development and correction program and carry out targeted activities;

Knowledge, skills and abilities are not the final goal of education, but they are a means of developing the individuality of the student, a creative person will show a creative approach in all activities in the future. According to scientists, a genre arises from the individuality of artists in their creative and professional activities, that is, the artist chooses a genre that he has a special love for, devoting the main part of his work to this genre, and creates his best works in this genre. .

The psychological-pedagogical description of the individual style in the creative activity of artists, the qualities necessary in the creative activity of artists can be divided into three groups according to their composition and leadership. The first group of qualities consists of neurophysiological innate ability, a unique communication with the external environment, the need and ability to mobilize the will for a long time and carry out one or various creative activities. Due to the fact that students are different in terms of personal qualities, if the task is easy for some, they lose interest in the activity, and if the task seems more difficult for some, they avoid failure and stop their activity, "it's up to me "It doesn't make sense", "it's not interesting for me" and refuses to create or perform a task. It is pointed out that such students should be given appropriate conversation, encouragement, psychological-pedagogical support, and the use of incentives.

The qualities of the second group include features such as cognitive processes, emotion, feeling, without denying innate ability.

The social environment plays a big role in the formation of the qualities of the third group, and the worldview, beliefs, interests and passions of the person formed as a result of them play an important role, life values, and the attitude towards the surrounding people.

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The purpose of dividing the qualities of the individuality of a creative person into three groups is to show which groups of characteristics are leading in the student, visual art is better mastered and perceived, and to whom it is necessary to have a pedagogical influence.

It is known that the history of the emergence of culture is measured by the emergence of man. Fine art is also a part of culture, and its history is derived from the history of art. Having knowledge and imagination about a number of people who are considered as the pillars of art history shows the cultural level of a modern person. It is important to equip schoolchildren with knowledge about visual art and its history of development in the perception of visual art works, as these aspects can serve as a function of forming a modern, cultured person in society. One of the ways to effectively fulfill this task is the need to teach the history of visual arts to young people at the school level.

After all, it provides students with relevant information about works of visual art and their authors, the main ideas in the works, teaching them to perceive works artistically and enjoy aesthetic pleasure, practical activities in teaching fine art, great artists, sculptors. information is valuable. It is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of the child in the formation of artistic perception. A very large number of people cannot distinguish colors, which negatively affects the correct and complete perception of a work of visual art. However, it is possible to teach the majority of students to correctly perceive colors and to identify the subtle differences between them within the framework of visual arts classes at school. As a result of not paying enough attention to this problem, a large part of the population remains, figuratively speaking, "color blind".

The issue of allowing students to enjoy cultural heritage is a big problem, and the pedagogical practice conducted with students on visual arts does not meet the requirements of the time, and it is methodologically lame, and the lack of interest in the history of art among young people needs to be solved. is one of the problems. According to historical data, due to the great attention paid to fine art and its history in education in Europe and Russia, large museums were established, great works of art were created, and architecture was highly developed.

REFERENCES:

1. Boymatov B., Tolipova N. Maktabda tasviriy san'at to'garagi. O'quv dastur. – Toshkent, 1995.
2. Pirnazarov G. F., Mamurova F. I., Mamurova D. I. Calculation of Flat Ram by the Method of Displacement //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 35-39.
3. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Directions For Improving Teaching Methods //Journal of Positive School Psychology. – 2022. – C. 9671–9678-9671–9678.
4. Aminov, A. S., Mamurova, D. I., & Shukurov, A. R. (2021, February). Additional and didactic game technologies on the topic of local appearance. In *E-Conference globe* (pp. 34-37).
5. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Information Technology in Education //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 17-22.
6. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Opportunities to use information technology to increase the effectiveness of education //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE). – 2022. – T. 14. – №. 02.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-6

7. Mamurova D., Khusnidinova N. Didactic possibilities of using computer graphics programs in the educational process //BIO Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2024. – T. 84. – C. 02020.
8. Mamurova D. I., Ibatova N. I., Badieva D. M. The importance of using the key-stadi innovative educational technology method in training the image module of geometric shapes //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 335-338.
9. Khodjayeva N. S., Yakhyayeva M. T. Calculate Exact Integrals in the Visual Basic Window of Excel //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 172-177.
10. Khodjayeva N., Sodikov S. Methods and Advantages of Using Cloud Technologies in Practical Lessons //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 77-82.
11. Khodjayeva, Nodira. "THE URGENCY OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN PROSPECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING." *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры* 3.5 (2023): 77-80.
12. Ibadullayeva S. "MANZARA JANRIDA IJOD QILGAN RASSOMLAR ASARIDAN NUSXA KO'CHIRISH" MODULINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH AHAMIYATI //Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1.
13. Ilkhamovna I. S. DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN FINE ARTS LESSONS //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 104-107.
14. Ilkhamovna I. S. THE ESSENCE AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE CONCEPT OF CREATIVE ABILITY //Role of Exact and Natural Sciences During the Renaissance III. – 2023. – C. 69-71.
15. Mamatov, Dilshod. "PROJECTS OF MAKING CLAY AND PLASTIC TOYS IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION." *Theoretical & Applied Science* 9 (2019): 281-285.
16. Mamatov, D. K. (2021, April). The importance of teaching architecture drawing in secondary schools. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 102-104).
17. Dilshod, M. (2024, March). IMPROVING THE COGNITIVE-COMPETENCE APPROACH TO TEACHING DRAWING AND DESCRIPTIVE GEOMETRY. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 31-35).
18. Ширинов А. Л., Батиров Д. С., Шомуродов О. Н. Важность цветоведения в изобразительном искусстве //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2021. – №. 5 (64). – С. 83-85.
19. Botirov, J. S., Bakaev, S. S., Avliyakov, M. M., Shirinov, A. L., & Abdullaev, S. S. (2021). The same goes for art classes in private schools specific properties. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government* Vol, 27(2).
20. Muzafarovna A. N., Jurayevich J. Q. The role of islam in folk decorative art of Bukhara //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – T. 9. – №. 5. – C. 347-350.
21. Muzafarovna A. N. THE ROLE OF ARTISTIC CREATIVITY IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE FINE ARTS TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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VOLUME-4, ISSUE-6

//Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.5
Pedagogical sciences.

22. Muzafarovna, A. N. (2023). IMPROVING FUTURE TEACHERS'SKILLS OF DESIGNING AND MODELING FINE ARTS LESSONS. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 21-24.

23. Muzafarovna A. N., Zubrilin K. M. DISCLOSURE OF STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS ABOUT THE TYPES OF PAPER USED IN FINE ARTS LESSONS AND PREPARING FOR THEIR WORK //Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 337-340.

24. Shomurodov O. N. Perception and depiction of basic color relationships in painting performance //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 11. – С. 62-65.

25. Shomurodov O. N. HAYKALTAROSHLIK TASVIRIY SAN'ATNING TURI SIFATIDA //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 51-57.

26. Шомуродов О. Н., Аvezов Ш. Н. Компьютерные технологии обучения //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2 (99). – С. 51-54.

